

P4-MTAGG - a Framework for Multi-Tenant P4 Network Devices

Fabian Brisch*, Andreas Kessler*[†], Sándor Laki[‡], Peter Hudoba[‡] and Gergely Pongracz[§]

*Institute of Applied Computer Science, Deggendorf Institute of Technology, Deggendorf, Germany

[†]Computer Science Department, Karlstads Universitet, Karlstad, Sweden

[‡]Faculty of Informatics, ELTE Eötvös Loránd University, Budapest, Hungary

[§]Ericsson Research, Budapest, Hungary

Email: *fabian.brisch@th-deg.de, andreas.kessler@th-deg.de [†]andreas.kessler@kau.se, [‡]lakis@inf.elte.hu,

[‡]peter.hudoba@inf.elte.hu, [§]gergely.pongracz@ericsson.com

Abstract—The current P4 programmability model assumes that a P4 programmable device is owned and controlled by a single tenant. However, in typical NFV scenarios, support for multiple tenants is desirable. When each tenant may want to deploy their own P4 pipeline offering different network functions (NF), supporting multiple co-existing tenant pipelines on a single platform is difficult because it requires pipeline merging, control plane support, and resource management of the platform. In this paper, we present P4-MTAGG, a novel framework for flexibly deploying multiple P4 programmable NFs on a programmable match-action pipeline while supporting multiple tenants. P4-MTAGG consists of i) novel compiler-additions for automatic merging multiple P4-pipelines, ii) p4runtime-proxy to allow for control plane access of the aggregated pipelines together with policy based resource management for the P4 target, and iii) orchestrator to automate the provisioning of a P4-based target utilizing aggregation either in a simulated or real hardware environment. We use a testbed equipped with Neutron SmartNIC to evaluate the throughput and latency of aggregated pipelines varying the complexity of individual ones. By comparing the performance of the aggregated pipelines with the non-aggregated ones, we show that the synthesized code creates overhead due to the usage of SRv6 and per tenant metering for resource management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) have emerged as an important paradigm for making networks more flexible and programmable. However, deploying network functions (NF) on commodity infrastructure limits the performance of the data plane. Recently, P4 has emerged as an important concept that enables data plane programmability supporting both software and hardware targets. Indeed, P4 has the promise to provide fast packet processing performance when deployed on hardware targets such as switching ASICs (e.g., Tofino) or FPGA-based packet processors while at the same time providing flexibility of software-based definition of networking functions. P4-based NFs can be implemented with less code compared to when implemented in a virtualized environment and can be deployed on multiple targets having different hardware capabilities (e.g. on a smartNIC, FPGA or on a CPU-based host).

However, the current P4 programmability model assumes that the hardware target is under the control of a single entity. Although some targets provide support of several parallel

pipelines, the current approach is to deploy these pipelines all under the same administrative control. While each pipeline may implement its own NF, still such approach supports only a single tenant. However, in cloud-based scenarios, the support of multiple tenants on a single common infrastructure is imperative. Consequently, multiple tenants can only be served with the same functionality [4]. However, different tenants may have the need to deploy different NFs as they want to implement different networking features or protocol versions.

Supporting multiple tenants in a single programmable target poses multiple challenges, including i) how to merge the individual tenants' NFs so that they can be deployed on the target (as the target typically has less pipelines than number of NFs of all tenants that should be deployed), ii) how to provide control plane access to individual tenants, as the merged NFs typically only expose a single control plane interface that all tenants must share and iii) how to manage the target resources between tenants, such as memory (e.g., TCAM entries, SRAM) processing power (e.g., processed packets per second) or control plane load (e.g., number of installed/updated rules per second).

Some recent works tackled similar issues. For example, μ P4 [5] proposes a novel programming language/framework based on the P4-standard that focuses on modularity and interoperability of different functions. However, support of different tenants is not provided. Placement of NFs and its impact on performance and resource consumption has been discussed in [3]. While it assumes that a host is capable of deploying multiple NFs, the process to support this has not been solved. Supporting multiple tenants on a single platform with implications on the control interface has been discussed in [1], but is limited to fixed-function multi-tenancy. Lemur [6] allows to merge multiple NFs but does not consider multiple tenants and resource sharing policies.

We propose P4-MTAGG, which is a framework to dynamically aggregate/merge and deploy different P4 programmable tenant pipelines composed of multiple NFs. P4-MTAGG consists of i) a meta-compile stage (MTAGG-CP) in order to merge different tenant NFs specified in P4 language to synthesize a single aggregated pipeline that supports the functionality of the different tenant NFs, ii) a control-plane proxy (MTAGG-

Proxy) which translates P4-Runtime requests for aggregated pipelines and enforces per-tenant resource allocation policies and iii) a central orchestrator automating the aggregation and deployment functionality. During the aggregation stage, P4-MTAGG merges individual NFs parsers, tables and processing logic and wires the individual NFs together using segment routing. It adds additional resource management functionality in the data plane by adding per tenant meters that are exposed to the control plane proxy to enable rate-limiting per tenant packet processing according to the resource sharing policies. We evaluate the impact of aggregation for Netronome Agilio SmartNIC on throughput and latency of the individual pipeline, what overhead is inflicted by additional functionality of the aggregated pipelines and how much impact larger NF size has on throughput. We also evaluate the impact of different traffic mixes on throughput and latency.

II. P4-MTAGG FRAMEWORK

The proposed framework consists of three key elements, the meta-compiler (MTAGG-CP), control plane proxy (MTAGG-PROXY) and the orchestrator (MTAGG-ORCH) (see Fig. 1). Running the framework requires a configuration describing tenants, NFs and resources available for NF deployment. The configuration consists of a set of P4 pipelines of all NFs with given SRv6-segment IDs [2] to be used for packet identification. The configuration further provides the MTAGG-ORCH with information about available targets to run the NFs.

Fig. 1. P4-MTAGG framework components

A. MTAGG-CP

The meta-compiler combines multiple P4-pipelines while preserving individual functionality and injecting additional functionality into the aggregated pipeline for resource management and monitoring. The meta-compiler i) merges individual parsers into a single one capable to parse packets as defined in all source pipelines, ii) combines the match-action stages from all pipelines, dealing with possible naming collisions and iii) adds additional tables and parser states to identify incoming packets based on SRv6-header and segment IDs provided in the configuration and apply the correct NF, collect statistics about per tenant NF packet processing rates and resource (e.g., bandwidth, memory) usage and apply rate-limiting to each NF as configured by the proxy.

The P4-MTAGG compiler extension is based on the T4P4S compiler, utilizing HLR-16 for internal P4-representation and manipulation. The compiler extension takes multiple .p4 files as input and outputs a .p4 file of the aggregated pipeline as well as p4runtime-information for use in the proxy.

B. MTAGG-PROXY

The MTAGG-PROXY serves as a bridge between the unmodified individual control planes of each tenant and the data plane in the post-aggregation topology. The proxy launches independent P4Runtime servers for each tenant and NF to control and isolate the control plane access to different data plane objects. Through the proxy the control plane of each NF and tenant can manage the NF data plane as if it exclusively use the data plane. It transforms the write and read messages according to the aggregation and forwards them to the appropriate data plane object in the aggregated pipeline. For each incoming requests, it maps the data plane object identifiers in the individual P4 programs to the identifiers used in the aggregated code. Then the messages are forwarded to the P4Runtime interface of the aggregated program. In the case of receiving a reply, it similarly translates the identifiers back and send them to the appropriate individual NF control plane. The configuration needed for the identifier-mapping functionality is determined in aggregation time by MTAGG-CP.

The configuration interface allows to manage resources for both control (amount of rules insert/update operations per second, table entries, registers, meters and counters - per tenant) and data planes (allowed packets and bytes per tenant processing rate). This information is used to configure the per-tenant meters in the synthesized aggregated data plane code (excess packets will be dropped) and rate regulates the control plane messages per tenant (regulating P4Runtime (gRPC) message rate on the proxy northbound), appropriately.

The proxy also has a persistency module that stores the control plane commands, so it is possible to upload the tables and configure the meters unnoticed by the controller layer in the case of failure or redeployment.

C. MTAGG-ORCH

Meta-Compiler and Proxy are controlled by the Orchestrator. It reads the framework config, executes the aggregation process and handles deployment of network functions. The Orchestrator also configures the proxy with addresses and ports of the aggregated program. The demo controller is implemented in python and can be configured with a set of network-functions as well as P4 targets. P4-MTAGG currently supports the following P4 targets: BMv2 switches in Mininet, Intel Tofino, Intel DPDK (through t4p4s) and Netronome Agilio SmartNIC.

D. Fairness

When deploying multiple NFs with different resource requirements on a single P4 target using P4-MTAGG, individual NFs compete for the P4 target's resources (such as registers and TCAM entries) and processing capacity. This is because

	NF1	NF2	NF3	Aggregation
Nr. of parsed headers (ex. eth,ipv6)	0	5	10	$\sum NF_{i,j}+2$
Nr. of tables	1	6	11	$\sum NF_{i,j}+1$
Hash-calculations	0	1	5	$\sum NF_{i,j}+0$

TABLE I
COMPLEXITY OF NETWORK FUNCTIONS

the amount of resources required to process a packet by a given NF can vary wildly depending on the complexity of the NF. This may have a detrimental effect on performance and fairness, especially on targets that use software packet processing (e.g. P4 compiled to DPDK) or smartNICs using Microengines for packet processing (e.g. Agilio family of SmartNIC from Netronome).

III. PERFORMANCE

Our evaluation focuses on the performance impact of deploying NFs in an aggregated environment by answering the following research questions:

- 1) What is the overhead of our aggregation approach?
- 2) How does mixing traffic load between two aggregated pipelines impact latency and throughput?
- 3) How can fairness between NFS be evaluated?

A. Evaluation Setup

To answer these questions, we use a Device under Test (DUT) equipped with a Netronome Agilio smartNIC 2x40G. We used Cisco T-Rex on another server to generate traffic, connected to the DUT via two 40g fiber links. All tests aim to find the maximal achievable non-drop rate (NDR) with 60 second iterations and are repeated 10 times. Packet structure is *Ethernet,IPv6,SRv6* with packet size of 128 bytes.

Fig. 2. Individual pipeline performance

B. Test Scenarios

All tests are conducted using the pipelines described in Table I and their respective 2-way aggregations. The individual pipelines are tested for NDR and packet latency. The aggregated pipelines are tested for NDR and latency at different traffic distributions:

- Isolated traffic: Similar to when a single pipeline is tested individually, the test traffic only contains packets for one of the two aggregated NFs.
- Mixed traffic: In mixed traffic scenarios packets for both NFs are being sent simultaneously. Distributions

tested from 0%/100% to 100%/0% with 10% increments/decrements. Latency is measured for each NF separately.

C. Results

Fig. 2 shows that performance significantly deteriorates when we run more complex (more tables, more complex parsers) P4-pipelines on the smartNIC. In addition, the performance of aggregated pipelines is worse than using the non-aggregated ones due to the additional parsing of header, tables and meters due to our synthesized code for managing per-tenant fairness. Observed latency increases are in line with performance differences, with a higher relative increase in latency for functions with lower individual latencies.

Fig. 3. Mixed traffic scenarios

Fig. 3 shows that when mixing traffic between two pipelines of different complexity the reached NDR changes linearly between the individual (aggregated) NF NDRs in Figure 2. Latency is also lower for the NF with less effort, but is affected by traffic mix.

The collected data also allows to calculate the fairness of a specific traffic mix. As a pure bandwidth-based fairness calculation does not represent the different efforts required to process a single packet in different NFs, the used bandwidth is based on cumulative packet handling time of the aggregated NFs (pps * latency). This calculation yields peak fairness at 20/80(NF1/NF3), 20/80(NF1/NF2) and 40/60(NF2/NF3).

D. Conclusion

This initial evaluation of the performance of aggregated p4-NFs shows that the aggregation process itself has an overhead impacting the overall performance of the NFs when aggregated. Mixing packet load between NFs affects overall throughput of the target, with NDR changing linearly depending on the traffic mix. A fair traffic distribution between two NFs with different effort can be calculated by using Jain's fairness index with bandwidths scaled by the single pipeline latency.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Parts of this work has been supported by the Bavarian State Ministry of Education and Culture, Science and Art through the High-Tech Agenda (HTA) and the Knowledge Foundation of Sweden (KKS) through project DRIVE. The research leading to these results has also received funding from the European Commission through the HORIZON 6G SNS JU DESIRE6G (G.A. 101096466). S. Laki also thanks the support of National Research, Development and Innovation Office - NKFIH, FK_21 138949.

REFERENCES

- [1] Buck Chung, Chien-Chao Tseng, Jim Hao Chen, and Joe Mambretti. P4MT: Multi-Tenant Support Prototype for International P4 Testbed. In *2019 ACM/IEEE Symposium on Architectures for Networking and Communications Systems (ANCS)*, pages 1–2, Cambridge, United Kingdom, September 2019. IEEE.
- [2] C. Filsfils, P. Camarillo, J. Leddy, D. Voyer, S. Matsushima, and Z. Li. Segment Routing over IPv6 (SRv6) Network Programming. Technical Report RFC8986, RFC Editor, February 2021.
- [3] Hasanin Harkous, Bassel Aboul Hosn, Mu He, Michael Jarschel, Rastin Pries, and Wolfgang Kellerer. Performance-Aware Orchestration of P4-Based Heterogeneous Cloud Environments. *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, 20(4):4765–4778, December 2023.
- [4] Mu He, Arsany Basta, Andreas Blenk, Nemanja Deric, and Wolfgang Kellerer. P4NFV: An NFV Architecture with Flexible Data Plane Reconfiguration. In *2018 14th International Conference on Network and Service Management (CNSM)*, pages 90–98, November 2018. ISSN: 2165-963X.
- [5] Hardik Soni, Myriana Rifai, Praveen Kumar, Ryan Doenges, and Nate Foster. Composing Dataplane Programs with P4. In *Proceedings of the Annual conference of the ACM Special Interest Group on Data Communication on the applications, technologies, architectures, and protocols for computer communication*, pages 329–343, Virtual Event USA, July 2020. ACM.
- [6] Jane Yen, Jianfeng Wang, Sucha Supittayapornpong, Marcos A. M. Vieira, Ramesh Govindan, and Barath Raghavan. Meeting SLOs in cross-platform NFV. In *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on emerging Networking EXperiments and Technologies*, pages 509–523, Barcelona Spain, November 2020. ACM.